

Forming Enterprise Skills and Skills in Children through Activity Games

Rakhmatullayev Talgat Ayazbekovich

Teacher of the Department of Children's Sports, Faculty of Preschool Education, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

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Abstract: In the article, the author studied the problem of forming initiative skills and competences in children of the preschool group through action games.

Keywords: Children, active games, children of preschool age, physical stress, physical exercises.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, physical education, sports and national games are taking a strong place in the educational system as the main means of education.

It is worth noting that the implementation of special tests "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" in life, various youth sports competitions, "Umid Nihollari", "Universiade", festivals of people's national games, as well as regular organization of spartakiades and championships in beer clubs of populated areas. Large sports facilities are being built in all regions and central cities, that is, sports schools, lyceums, vocational colleges are being established.

All of us are witnesses of the fact that during the years of independence, many things are being carried out that raise the stature of our nation, glorify its pride, add pride to its pride, and create a foundation for the realization of its centuries-old dreams.

A healthy generation, bringing up our children as mature and perfect people in all respects, considering them as the owners of our future, as an issue directly related to the future of the nation, has become an integral part of the independence policy, and it serves this noble purpose.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The most honorable dream of any person, the main goal that he strives for is to raise a healthy and perfect generation, to bring up a perfect person in all aspects.

Initiative is carried out by being an organizer of positive activities and events in the family, neighborhood, community, and becoming an active participant in the implementation of creative ideas.

The goals and tasks of physical education are determined by the needs of society. This need arises from the general goal of education, which is the formation of a harmoniously developed person who embodies spiritual wealth, moral purity and physical perfection. When solving the tasks of physical education of preschool children, their age characteristics are taken into

account. Rapid growth and development is a characteristic feature of a child's organism of preschool age. But the formation of systems and their tasks will not be completed.

That's why a preschooler is very sensitive. In this regard, the following health care tasks are prioritized:

- to protect life, to fight against diseases, to increase the body's resistance to the effects of the external environment;
- correct and timely development of all systems of the body, expansion of their functional capabilities, correct height - formation of height and heel, harmonious physical development.

Along with the imperfection and delicacy of the children's body, it also has features that ensure powerful development. A child adapts to changes in conditions and physical stress much faster and better than adults. He will be able to acquire knowledge and skills that are understandable to him, which will allow him to solve a number of educational tasks:

- formation of preliminary knowledge related to engaging in physical exercises and mastering cultural and hygienic skills;
- instilling personal and social hygiene skills;
- formation of the skills and abilities of vital actions that will serve as a basis for practicing sports in the future.

Physical exercises help children's complete intellectual, moral, aesthetic and work education, develop their spiritual and willful qualities (courage, honesty, determination, etc.).

When working with children of preschool and junior school age, these rules are expressed in the following. The rule of all-round development of the personality ensures the formation of the foundations of the movement culture and at the same time the development of mental abilities (ingenuity, observation, interest, etc.), moral qualities (discipline, community, etc.), aesthetic taste. Premature specialization in one or another type of physical exercise cannot be allowed. It can harm the child's health and harmonious physical development, create difficulties in the formation and formation of new skills and sports skills.

The rule of the direction of health care provides for the selection of the content and size of materials and tools, it ensures the strengthening of health, the implementation of the doctor-pedagogue control.

A special place is given to various games in the agenda of the preschool educational institution. In order to make full use of time, it is necessary for the educator to select toys and manuals in advance, to train children in performance skills.

Physical exercises play an important role in working with preschool children. In the period from 3 to 7 years old, children should learn to play various action games under the guidance of a teacher and independently, mastering basic movements, sports exercises. This broad program can only be accomplished by using a variety of tools and forms of work.

Due to the characteristics of physical and mental development of children during this period, the following specific tasks are identified:

- complete and harmonious physical development, training the cardiovascular and respiratory system, shaping height and legs;
- training the body;
- to educate the skills of performing all basic movements, sports exercises;
- development of physical abilities, initiative qualities;

➤ education of habits of freedom and orderliness.

What should be paid attention to in raising and developing children physically fit for educators and parents. What kind of training is important in this regard? First of all, what physical qualities and skills should be developed? What is more important for a child who has entered the age of rapid development - to control his body or to be strong, agile, resilient, to acquire knowledge, to be aware of new information and information, or to be aware of his own Do you know how to express your opinion? Both directions are very important in this matter. Because any deficiency in this direction will be known soon.

People involved in raising children should understand that physical and mental development go hand in hand. It is necessary to continue this process, education, especially for children aged 3-6 years, because physical health, curiosity, learning of the surrounding world, will, and skills to overcome difficulties are created in these young people.

CONCLUSION

It is necessary to hold public performances of teams of pre-school educational institutions on jogging, cycling paths, and in the swimming pool, separately from the performances of schoolchildren and adults, at hours and days convenient for children. The results shown by the teams of pre-school educational institutions are included in the general account.

Sports holidays organized in the open air are very beneficial for children's health and training. During the holiday, it is necessary to take into account children's clothes and ensure high movement activity.

In order to hold sports holidays in the room, it is necessary to follow the real rules and not allow the children to spend time outdoors. Wide use of nearby sports facilities - stadium, arena, sports halls, swimming pool, etc. is recommended.

One of the important requirements for organizing holidays is to hold them in different seasons. Accordingly, they can be held in different natural conditions. For example, a sports holiday can be organized not only in the territory of preschool educational institutions, but also in a camp, a stadium, in natural conditions - a garden, a pond, a river. In many cases, the theme, structure, preparation and equipment of the celebration depend on the place of celebration. Public organizations, employees of sports facilities, sponsors are involved in the organization of sports holidays. It is appropriate to take into account the peculiarities of the climate-geographical, economic, social conditions, the characteristics of the national traditions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, regions, and districts when creating the holiday program, determining its theme, and choosing its content and equipment.

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